

Colloid-Chemical Behaviour of the Reaction Products of Pyrophosphoric Acid with Copper (II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Vanadyl(II)

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The qualitative measure of the polymerisation effect on the complexes of Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), VO(II) with $H_4P_2O_7$ effect was studied by conductometric studies. To measure this effect quantitatively, colloidal studies were performed. In this connection, changes of ζ -potential on addition of the electrolyte as well as non electrolytes, the change of pH on their addition were measured. From these studies it was concluded that all of them form the polymerised product of the type $[M(H_2P_2O_7)]_x^{2-x}$ where x corresponds to $[M(H_2P_2O_7)_2]^{2-}$

CONDUCTOMETRIC and pH metric studies on the reactions of heavy metal ions with pyrophosphoric acid carried out in this laboratory have provided evidence for the existence of simple and polymeric ionic species in the reaction mixture. The species undergoing polymerisation is represented by the general formula : $H_2[M(H_2P_2O_7)_2]$. This behaviour was considered worth investigating from purely colloidal point of views and forms the main theme of this communication.

Preliminary investigations revealed that stable colloidal solutions were obtained on mixing the dilute solutions in appropriate portion without adding any peptising agents. From this behaviour it was surmised that in metal pyrophosphate the charge on the electrical double layer originated from the structural characteristic of the compound. Furthermore the resulting product underwent gelation on mixing concentrated solutions of the reactants.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions : All the four metal salts, i. e., $Co(NO_3)_2$, $CuCl_2$, $NiCl_2$ and $VOCl_2$ used were of AnalaR Grade (B. D. H. product). The pyrophosphoric acid and sodium pyrophosphate were of E.MERCK product. All the solutions were made in conductivity water.

Apparatus : All the vessels used were of pyrex glass. They were thoroughly washed and steamed before using. The ζ -potential of the sol was determined by measuring the cataphoretic velocity of the colloidal particles by means of a modified Burton's cataphoresis apparatus using non-polarisable electrodes¹. pH measurements were carried out with the help of a Elico(India) meter Model LI-10 after standardising with potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer (pH 4.0) and Borax buffer (pH 9.10).

Preparation of colloidal solutions and gels: 50 ml of $H_4P_2O_7$ solution (0.2M) was taken in 100 ml measuring flask. To this 25 ml of 0.2M metal salt was added in small aliquots with constant shaking. The solution was then made upto the mark by the requisite amount of conductivity water. Stable colloidal solution ranging from bluish green to pink colour were obtained.

Optimum conditions for gelation were realised also only for the stoichiometric ratio (1 : 2) and a rigid gel was obtained instantaneously on mixing the reactants (2 molar each).

Results and Discussion

Nature of charge on colloidal particles : Conductometric and pH-metric titrations show that the metal and pyrophosphate react in the ratio of 1 : 2. The reaction may be represented by the following equation :

where $M^{2+} = Co^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Ni^{2+}$ and VO^{2+} and $L^- = NO_3^-$ and Cl^- .

Since the reactions are carried out at low pH (below 3.5), the reacting species of pyrophosphoric acid would be $H_2P_2O_7^{2-}$. The complex anion thus obtained can undergo aggregation to give particles of colloidal dimensions. Aggregation of such species would give a negatively charged colloidal micelle of the type shown

Fig. 1—Variation of ζ -potential on addition of electrolytes to cobalt pyrophosphate sol.

tial in presence of added electrolyte (typical plots for cobalt are shown in Fig. 1) show that the ζ -potential

decreases steadily and slowly on increasing the concentrations of the electrolyte. An examination of these curves show that in the case of $AlCl_3$, the fall in ζ -potential is very small even for a large concentration of $AlCl_3$ and hence no coagulation is observed on its addition. In the case of KCl and $BaCl_2$ larger changes in ζ -potential are observed and these electrolytes coagulate the sol to some extent while in the case of $Th(NO_3)_4$ the ζ -potential falls to quite a low value (above 5 mv) and hence it shows appreciable coagulation. Failure of complete coagulation at a low ζ -potential of 5 mV shows that the colloidal micelle is hydrated, again the fact that the origin of charge lies in the inherent negative charge on the polymerised anions of the complex.

Studies on the changes in ζ -potential in presence of varying amounts of alcohols show that the sol particles are associated with a strongly adsorbed water layer; The ζ -potential of each sol decrease with the increasing amount of alcohol. The decrease in ζ -potential is in the order methanol < ethanol < butanol i.e. in the order of their increasing dehydrating capacities (methanol > ethanol > butanol). These observations go to prove the existence of hydration shell or the colloidal micelle. The gels show thixotropic behaviour as evinced by the fact that the gel structure which got destroyed on shaking, was again realised on keeping for approximately 2 hr. The respective colour of the copper, cobalt, nickel, iron manganese and vanadyl gels were whitish blue, pink, greenish white, white, white and bluish white. A colourless transparent of the gel was obtained in the case of thorium.